

Activity-Concentration Data for Water in Organic Solvents

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A vapor pressure method has been used to obtain activity data for solutions of water in the solvents acetophenone, nitrobenzene, dibutylphthalate, and N,N-dimethylaniline at temperatures in the range 28°-55°, 25°-55°, 20°-50°, and 18°-50°, respectively. Departures of measured activities from linear dependence on concentration are attributed to formation of polymeric water species at very low solute concentration. Enthalpies of formation of hydrogen bonds in water dimers and trimers are estimated from the temperature dependence of association constants.

ACTIVITY data were reported previously for water in several organic solvents; water was shown to deviate significantly from Henry's law behavior even at very low concentrations³. To extend this work we have now investigated the partial vapor pressure of water above its solutions in the relatively nonvolatile solvents N,N-dimethylaniline, acetophenone, dibutylphthalate, and nitrobenzene. The temperature was varied over about 30° for each system to permit calculation of enthalpies of assumed polymeric species of water.

Experimental

The vapor pressure of water was measured as a function of formal concentration at the required temperatures. The method used is very similar to one described earlier⁴. Exactly 100 ml of the pure solvent is introduced into the solution flask. The entire system is immersed in a thermostatted water bath, and evacuated to the vapor pressure of the nonvolatile solvent (very few torr, if any). Samples of pure water ranging from 0.01 to 0.4 ml are introduced into the system through the mercury-covered sintered-glass disc. The pressure is measured after each addition, and additions are continued until the desired amount of water is introduced. It is known that the amount of dissolved air entering the system with water is so small that no air-pressure correction is needed before using the recorded pressures in any subsequent calculations.

Results and Discussion

Figures 1, 2, 3 and 4 show the variation of the partial pressure of water with its formal concentration in solution in acetophenone, nitrobenzene, dibutylphthalate and N,N-dimethylaniline, respectively, at the various temperatures investigated. The lines are calculated and the points are experimental.

The data, were treated with a computer program, similar to one described before^{3,5} designed to calculate the values of the least squares parameters and

Fig. 1. Variation of Total Pressure with Formal Concentration of Water in Solution in Acetophenone.

root mean square deviation (RMSD) in formal concentrations of water obtained for various choices of associated species.

Table 1 lists values of RMSD in formal concentrations of water. Table 2 summarizes the values of the thermodynamic functions and standard errors obtained.

Fig. 2. Variation of Total Pressure with Formal Concentration of Water in Solution in Nitrobenzene.

Fig. 4. Variation of Total Pressure with Formal Concentration of Water in Solution in N,N-dimethylaniline.

Fig. 3. Variation of Total Pressure with Formal Concentration of Water in Solution in Dibutylphthalate.

It was possible at all temperatures to obtain a good fit, in terms of RMSD, by assuming monomers and one polymeric species. The introduction of a second polymeric species did not in most cases significantly improve the fit, and in a few cases led to negative values of parameters.

Table 1 shows the RMSD when assuming monomer-dimer, monomer-trimer, or monomer-tetramer equilibria for the solution of water in acetophenone. It was possible to select the monomer-dimer equilibrium as being superior to the other ones on the basis of the RMSD and the progression of values of the constants for the sets of assumed species. This conclusion disagrees with that reported by Johnson, *et al.*³ who postulated that the monomer-trimer equilibrium was the most probable one at 25°, the only temperature at which measurements were made.

It can be also seen from Table 1 that, at 25°, the monomer-dimer assumption for water in nitrobenzene resulted in a lower RMSD than the monomer-trimer, whereas the latter is a better fit at all the higher temperatures. The assumption that at 25° monomers and dimers are the most likely species present substantiates the results obtained previously³. It is also not too surprising however, that larger polymeric species become more important at the higher temperatures. Farnham⁶, for example, while investigating some fluorinated alcohols, found that monomer-dimer fits are better at low temperatures, but that it is necessary to use monomer-dimer-trimer fits at higher temperatures. This might be explained on

TABLE 1

Solvent	Temp (°C)	Species	RMSD (molar)	
Acetophenone	28	1:2	0.000608	
		1:3	0.001654	
		1:4	0.002951	
	35	1:2	0.000820	
		1:3	0.001860	
		1:4	0.003198	
	45	1:2	0.003390	
		1:3	0.003750	
		1:4	0.004578	
	55	1:2	0.001239	
		1:3	0.001280	
		1:4	0.002269	
	Nitrobenzene	25	1:2	0.000564
			1:3	0.000589
			1:2	0.000503
35		1:3	0.000427	
		1:2	0.001614	
45		1:3	0.000744	
		1:2	0.000970	
55		1:3	0.000608	
		1:2	0.000608	
Dibutylphthalate	20	1:2	0.00170	
		1:3	0.00150	
	30	1:2	0.00136	
		1:3	0.00052	
	40	1:2	0.00326	
		1:3	0.00183	
	50	1:2	0.00292	
		1:3	0.00078	
	N,N-dimethylaniline	18	1:3	0.00099
			1:4	0.00131
		25	1:3	0.00054
			1:4	0.00055
40		1:3	0.00060	
		1:4	0.00092	
50		1:3	0.00087	
		1:4	0.00097	

the basis of solute-solvent interaction where it can be suggested that at lower temperatures, nitrobenzene may stabilize species such as

but as the temperature is raised, the solvent-solute interaction becomes weaker, and at the higher total water concentrations, mass action promotes formation of larger water aggregates.

Using dibutylphthalate as a solvent, the experimental data could be best fitted by assuming a monomer-trimer equilibrium. It was reported before³ that water exists in this solvent as a monomer-dimer equilibrium at 25° only. In the present work, this system was studied at 20°, 30°, 40° and 50°, and at all these temperatures it is obvious from Table 1 that the root mean square deviation for the monomer-trimer fit is much less than that for the monomer-dimer one. It is also interesting to notice that the difference between the RMSD for the 1:2 and the 1:3 fits is small at low temperatures whereas it

becomes relatively high as the temperature is increased. This phenomenon resembles that observed in case of nitrobenzene and could be accounted for on the same basis.

Regarding the structure of water polymers in its solution in N,N-dimethylaniline, the trimer is also believed to be the most probable species present. This is in good agreement with the conclusion reached by Johnson, *et al.*³ who reported a value of 26.98 molar⁻² for the trimerization constant at 25°, compared to a value of 23.00 molar⁻² obtained in this work for the same temperature.

Concerning the structure of the water trimers formed, Holmes, Kivelson and Drinkard⁷ have assumed the presence of cyclic water³ trimers to explain a proton-exchange mechanism in non-aqueous media. Also, from proton magnetic resonance spectra for solutions in chloroform, Cohen and Reid⁸ have argued that such a trimer complex is stabilized by cooperative inductive effects. However, there have been numerous discussions of this point in the literature, and recently Tucker and Becker have argued from extensive spectral and vapor pressure data that the linear trimer is a major species in solutions of alcohols in nonpolar solvents⁹.

From the temperature dependence of the homo-association constants, K_n^s , it was possible to estimate the enthalpy of the association reaction of water in the various solvents from the relationship

$$\frac{d \ln K_n^s}{d(1/T)} = -\frac{\Delta H}{R}$$

Values of these enthalpies are listed in Table 2.

The solvents used in this work vary in their degree of polarity according to their molecular structure:

N,N-dimethylaniline acetophenone dibutylphthalate nitrobenzene from which it may be expected that the polarity increases roughly in the order: N,N-dimethylaniline < acetophenone < dibutylphthalate < nitrobenzene. On comparing the thermodynamic functions of association of water in these solvents, it appears that the strength of the hydrogen bond decreases as the polarity of the solvent increases. This might be expected in view of the increased solvation ability of the solvent as its polarity increases, which will decrease the tendency for water to form self-associated aggregates.

These results are in fair agreement with the previous observation that thermodynamic functions will decrease in the order of increasing solvent-solute interaction^{10,11}.

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TABLE 2

Solvent	Temp.	K^H (torr molar ⁻¹)	K_2^S (molar ⁻¹)	K_3^S (molar ⁻²)	ΔH
Acetophenone	28	49.86 ± 0.21	0.613 ± 0.015	—	-2.96 ± 0.113 K.cal/mole of dimers
	35	71.11 ± 0.37	0.538 ± 0.016	—	
	45	110.21 ± 1.54	0.495 ± 0.042	—	
	55	161.03 ± 1.32	0.401 ± 0.023	—	
Nitrobenzene	25	157.84 ± 0.74	—	2.726 ± 0.151	-4.01 ± 0.089 K.cal/mole of trimers
	35	225.73 ± 0.77	—	2.073 ± 0.077	
	45	321.55 ± 1.35	—	1.771 ± 0.067	
	55	494.43 ± 1.91	—	1.448 ± 0.057	
Dibutylphthalate	20	196.02 ± 1.11	—	2.739 ± 0.160	-4.59 ± 0.087 K.cal/mole of trimers
	30	146.10 ± 0.63	—	2.237 ± 0.066	
	40	217.45 ± 1.86	—	1.670 ± 0.064	
	50	317.41 ± 0.97	—	1.304 ± 0.018	
N,N-dimethylaniline	18	301.86 ± 14.03	—	45.44 ± 14.38	-11.42 ± 0.32 K.cal/mole of trimers
	25	392.02 ± 5.30	—	23.00 ± 2.97	
	40	630.08 ± 5.47	—	9.66 ± 0.85	
	50	848.50 ± 6.99	—	5.98 ± 0.65	

K^H = Henry's law constant.

K_n^S = Homo-association constant.

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